

Comparative Analysis of Squatting Facets on Femur, Tibia, and Talus: Insights from A Population in Northwest Uttar Pradesh and Cross – Population Comparisons

Stuti Srivastava¹, Abeer Zubair Khan², Kiran Chigurupalli³, Karam Vir Singh⁴, Neel Kamal Arora⁵, Mahboobul Haque⁶

¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Ananta Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Center, Kaliwas, Rajsamand district, Rajasthan, India

²Associate professor, Department of Anatomy, Hind Institute of Medical Sciences, Barabanki, Uttar Pradesh, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Radiation Oncology, Ananta Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Center, Kaliwas, Rajsamand district, Rajasthan, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology Venereology & Leprosy, Sarojini Naidu Medical College, Agra, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁵Professor, Department of Anatomy, Shri Ram Murti Smarak Institute of Medical Sciences, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India

⁶Professor, Department of Anatomy, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 29-04-2023 / Revised: 20-05-2023 / Accepted: 30-05-2023

Corresponding author: Dr Stuti Srivastava

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

The aim of this study was to compare the occurrence and size of squatting facets on the talus, femur, and tibia in a population from northwest U.P with previous studies conducted on different populations and races.

Materials and Methods: A total of 231 dry adult human bones (75 femurs, 75 tibias, and 81 tali) were examined. Measurements were taken using a digital Vernier caliper.

Results: Squatting facets were present in 49.33% of the femurs, 48.64% of the tibias, and 60.49% of the tali. The average length, width, and area of the femoral facets were 15.34±6.13mm, 12.24±5.54mm, and 128.08±63.71mm², respectively. On the tibia, the average length was 21.67±9.85mm, width was 6.96±2.44mm, and area was 101.42±52.13mm². The mean length, width, and area of the medial facets on the talus were 6.75±3.73mm, 4.02±2.40mm, and 17.61±10.20mm², respectively. The length of the lateral squatting facets on the talus was 9.89±5.28mm, width was 5.43±3.10mm, and area was 38.12±18.15mm².

Conclusion: Squatting facets are a direct result of changes in lifestyle. The higher occurrence of lateral squatting facets in the talus in this sample can be attributed to an uneven distribution of body weight, particularly towards the lateral side of the foot. It is also concluded that the incidence of these facets in the current sample is higher compared to Europeans, possibly due to different postural habits and lifestyle factors. These findings can be utilized as an anthropological indicator for distinguishing racial and regional characteristics of unidentified bones.

Keywords: Squatting Facets on Femur, Tibia, and Talus.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Squatting is a posture of ease and comfort frequently adopted by many communities and ethnic groups and populations in Asia and Africa. The posture allows a sitter to support the entire body on the feet, which remain the only parts of the human anatomy on the ground. Squatting is an acquired posture learnt right from infancy. Continuous and prolonged squatting performance engenders minor but identifiable changes in many bones of the lower limb. The dorsum talar neck often shows such a facet: it is caused by the abutment of the lower end of the on the talus. The corresponding area of juxtaposition on tibia also may show an identifiable facet [1,2]. These features are population specific and show racial variations also. [3]

The distal end of the tibia is expanded slightly and has anterior, medial, posterior, lateral, and distal surfaces [4,5,6]. It also has an inferomedial projection called the medial malleolus. The smooth anterior surface bulges beyond the distal surface and is separated by a narrow groove. The capsule of the ankle joint is attached to an anterior groove near the articular surface [7,8]. Remodeling of bone occurs in response to physical stress. Habitual squatting is associated with modifications of the neck of the talus (squatting facets) and its trochlear/malleolar surfaces (trochlear extensions), and individual populations exhibit different incidences of these modifications that reflect their lifestyle [9-13].

Talus is the key bone that links the leg and foot through the ankle joint (14). Though it carries the whole weight of the human body, it has neither tendon nor muscular attachments [15]. There are three articulating surfaces on the talus. The superior articular or the trochlear surface

of talus is concave transversely and convex parasagittally. It is wider in front. The articular surface for medial malleolus on talus is deep anteriorly and is comma shaped. The lateral talar surface is triangular and concave vertically [16]. The dimensions of these articular surfaces act as useful in making the ankle implants and for total ankle replacements [17,18]. There is limited data on morphometry of the human tali in North Indian population, and this study will be of use to radiologists, sports therapists and surgeons for diagnosis and treatment of talar neck fractures and in making the talar body prosthesis & in the treatment of congenital talipes equinovarus (CTEV) or club foot, to identify the degrees of pes cavus and pes planus and also will be of great help to forensic anthropologists [19,20,21].

Material and Method:

- The present study was conducted in a Tertiary Teaching Hospital on 230 dry adult human bones of unknown age and sex:
 - 75 femurs (34 – right, 41 – left)
 - 74 tibias (37 – right, 37 – left)
 - 81 tali (40 – right, 41 – left)
- Bones showing osteoporotic changes, osteophytes, with apparent pathology or physical damage were eliminated.
- The presence of squatting facets was noted and photographed.
- The outlines of the squatting facets were marked with a 2HB pencil.
- Impressions were taken on the butter paper.
- The area was calculated on graph paper.
- The maximum measurements were taken along the two axes of the facet i.e., length and breadth, using digital Vernier caliper.

Table: 1

S No.	Bone	Squatting facet location
1.	Femur	Infero – medial to the adductor tubercle on the infero – medial angle of the popliteal surface. Figure 1.
2.	Tibia	The anterior border of the tibia is in contact with the dorsum of the neck of talus. Figure 2.
3.	Talus	Lateral squatting facet: dorsum of the neck of the talus and usually continuous with the lateral trochlear surface. Figure 3. Medial squatting facet: dorsomedial aspect of the neck of the talus, that is not continuous with the trochlear surface. Figure 3.

(M) Squatting facets on Talus
Figure 3: Lateral (L) and Medial

Results

- **Femur:** There was presence of squatting facets on 37 bones (49.33%). It was seen more on left than right. The measurements (mean) were Length: $15.34 \pm 6.13\text{mm}$; Breadth: $12.24 \pm 5.54\text{mm}$ and Area: $128.08 \pm 63.71\text{mm}^2$. Figure 4, 5 and 6.
- **Tibia:** The presence of squatting facet was seen on 36 bones (48.64%). It was seen more on left. The measurements (mean) recorded were Length: $21.67 \pm 9.85\text{mm}$; Breadth: $6.96 \pm 2.44\text{mm}$ and Area: $101.42 \pm 52.13\text{mm}^2$. Figure 7, 8 and 9.
- **Talus:** On 49 bones (60.49%) squatting facets were seen. It was seen more on the left. The Lateral squatting facets were seen more than the medial squatting facets.
- **Lateral squatting facets:** The measurements (mean) recorded were Length: $9.89 \pm 5.28\text{mm}$; Breadth: $5.43 \pm 3.10\text{mm}$ and Area: $38.12 \pm 18.15\text{mm}^2$. Figure 10, 11, 12.
- **Medial squatting facets:** The measurements (mean) were Length: $6.75 \pm 3.73\text{mm}$; Breadth: $4.02 \pm 2.40\text{mm}$ and Area: $17.61 \pm 10.20\text{mm}^2$. Figure 13, 14, 15.

Figure 4: Length on femur

Figure 5: Breadth on femur

Figure 6: Area on femur

Figure 7: Length on Tibia

Figure 8: Breadth on Tibia

Figure 9: Area on Tibia

Figure 10: Length of Lateral squatting facet on talus

Figure 11: Breadth of Lateral squatting facet on talus

Figure 12: Area of Lateral squatting facet on talus

Figure 13: Length of Medial squatting facet on talus

Figure 14: Breadth of Medial squatting facet on talus

Figure 15: Area of Medial squatting facet on talus

Discussion

Kumar A et al have documented, 104 out of 108 adult femora from the West Coastal region of India show a distinct identifiable squatting facet on their popliteal surface [20]. Arunachalam K have studied 40 femur bones out of which 32 bones have visible and palpable facets & confirmed that femora from Indians show a femoral facet caused by squatting on a very consistent scale²¹. In the present study 37 bones femur out of 75 femurs have shown squatting facets. This drastic difference between the studies might be due to lifestyle changes in people's life as the need for squatting has significantly decreased.

Kumar S et al[22] have studied 30 tibia bones, of which 36.6% have facets on them. In the present study 36(48.64%) of 74 bones have facets, which is on a higher side.

Dixit SG et al[23] studied 147 tali in North Indian population and found 97 (65.9%) bones to have lateral squatting facets and only 12 (8.2%) to have medial squatting facets. Javia M et al[24] also studied 221 bones, in which 114 (51.58%) had lateral squatting facet and 6 (2.72%) had medial squatting facet. Garg et al[25] have studied 300 tali, of which 136(45.3%) have lateral squatting facet and 23(7.7%) have medial squatting facet. In the present study out of 81 tali, 48(59.25%) have lateral squatting

facet and 21(25.92%) have medial squatting facet.

In the present study incidence of squatting facet was found more on the left than right side. This may be because the habitual weight bearing limb is left. Higher incidence of lateral squatting facet in talus in this sample can be attributed to unequal distribution of body weight mainly towards lateral side of foot. The later reports of decrease incidence over the years can be attributed to the change in postural habits of the population. These modifications offer an opportunity to study the relationship between past and modern population and describes the daily activity of life and cultural structure.

Conclusion

Squatting facet is a direct consequence of lifestyle modifications. The incidence of facet in the present sample is higher as compared to Europeans due to different postural habits and commodities. This can be used as an anthropological marker for racial and regional differentiation of unidentified bones.

References

1. Singh. I, Squatting facets on the talus and tibia in Indians. J Anat. 1959; 93: 540.
2. Study of squatting facets in tibia and talus in South Indian Population, Shishirkumar, Nambiar. S,

- Arunachalam Kumar, International Journal of Science and Research. June 2014; 3:6.
3. Javia M, Changani M, Chudasama J, Thummar B, Vadgama J, Bambhaniya A. Morphological study of squatting facets on the neck of the talus in Indian population. *J Res Med Den Sci.* 2014; 2(4): 38-41.
 4. Mandela Pamela, Misiani Musa, Ogeng'o Julius, Obimbo Moses, GikenyeGichambira. Estimation of the length of the tibia from dimensions of the distal articular surfaces of the tibia in adult Kenyans. *International J. of Healthcare & Biomedical Research* 2013;1(4):250-257.
 5. Misiani Musa, Nderitu Joseph, Mandela Pamela, Obimbo Moses, Gikenye.
 6. Sexual dimorphism in the morphometric characteristics of the tibial plafond and medial malleolus. *Indian Journal of Basic & Applied Medical Research.* 2013;2(7):760-763.
 7. DeSilva JM. Functional morphology of the ankle and the likelihood of climbing in early hominins. 2009;106(16):6567-6572.
 8. Bruce D, Beynnon, Darlene F, Murphy, Denise M. Alosa Predictive Factors for Lateral Ankle Sprains. *J Athl Train.* 2002;37(4):376-380.
 9. Andrew Fauth R. Anatomically based investigations of total ankle arthroplasty. A thesis in kinesiology. 2005.
 10. Rosdi Daud, Mohammed Rafiq Abdul Kadir, Sudin Izman, Amir Putra Md Saad, Muhammad Hisyam Lee, Aminudin Che Ahmad. Three-dimensional morphometric study of the trapezium shape of the trochlea tali. *The journal of foot & ankle surgery.* 2013; 1-6.
 11. Andrea Hayes, Yuki Tochigi, Charles L. Saltzman. Ankle morphometry on 3d-ct images. *Iowa Orthop J.* 2006; 26:1-4.
 12. Chimba Mkandawire, William Ledoux R, Bruce J Sangeorzan, Randal Ching P. Foot and ankle ligament morphometry. *J Rehabil Res Dev.* 2005;42(6):809-20.
 13. MahmutUğurlu, Murat Bozkurt, İsmail Demirkale, AyhanCömert, Halil İbrahim Acar, İbrahim Tekdemir. Anatomy of the lateral complex of the ankle joint in relation to peroneal tendons, distal fibula, and talus: a cadaveric study. *Eklemler Hastalıkları Cerrahisi.* 2010;21(3):153-158.
 14. Gray's Anatomy. The Anatomical Basis of clinical practice. 40th edition, Elsevier Churchill Livingstone. 2008; 4279.
 15. Motagi MV, Kottapurath SR and Kavitarati D. Morphometric analyses of human dry tali of South Indian origin. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Public Health.* 2015; 4(2): 237-240.
 16. Khadija I, Sundus A and Shirza N. Anatomical variations of trochlear surface of talus. *Journal of University Medical and Dental College.* 2012; 3(1): 38-41.
 17. Ughade HM, Bhele AV and Shaikh S. Morphometric study of human talus - a cross sectional study. *International Journal of Anatomy and Research.* 2017; 5(3.2):4265-4268.
 18. Peeters K, Schreuer J, Burg F, Behets C, Van Bouwel S, Dereymaeker G, et al. Altered talar and navicular bone morphology is associated with pes planus deformity: A CT-scan study. *Journal of Orthopaedic and Research.* 2013; 31(2):282-287.
 19. Yu-Chi Huang. The relationship between the flexible flatfoot and plantar fasciitis: Ultrasonographic evaluation. *Chang Gung Medical Journal.* 2004; 27:443-447
 20. Kumar A., & Koranne S. P. The squatting facet on femora of West Coastal Indian population. *Forensic Science International,* 1983; 21(1): 19-21.

21. Kumar A and Shivarama C. International Journal of Scientific Research and Education. 2015; 3(7): 3995-3997.
22. Kumar S, Nambiar S, Kumar A. Study of squatting facets in tibia and talus in South Indian population. International Journal of Science and Research. June 2014; 3(6).
23. Dixit SG, Kaur J, Kakar S. Racial variation on articular surface of talus (astragalus) in North Indian population. J Forensic Leg Med. 2012; 19(3):152-7.
24. Javia M, Changani M, Chudasama J, Thummar B, Jignesh Vadgama J, Bambhaniya A. Morphological study of squatting facets on the neck of the talus in Indian population. Journal of Research in Medical and Dental Science. October- December 2014; 2(4): 38-41.
25. Garg R, Shekhawat S, Mogra K, Kumar S. Modifications on dorsum of neck of talus (squatting facets and trochlear extensions) in Indians. Acta Medica International. Jan-Jun 2015; 2(1): 100-104.